

M.Samandarova

*BukhSU, Organization and management of cultural and art institutions educational direction 3-
Stage Student*

Annotation: in this article, the national culture and national values of the Uzbek people are widely promoted through the eyes of foreign experts, in the era of globalization and technology, Uzbekistan cherishes its rich cultural heritage, at the same time trying to introduce it into time. From museums and cultural centers, which preserve and promote folk applied art, to educational programs and festivals aimed at studying and developing the cultural heritage of the navqiran generation, to the need to be widely promoted in our country.

Base words: Uzbek people, folk Applied Art, festival, Museum, Culture, National Culture, value, tradition, tradition.

When we plunge into the abyss of the national culture of the Uzbek people, we get an incredibly rich and colorful treasure trove of traditions and traditions. Centennial historical events, religious beliefs, deeply rooted social norms and values are considered to be full of this world. The national culture of the Uzbek people is a magnificent mosaic, consisting of many folk traditions that have survived for centuries and remain an important part of the life of modern society. The national culture of the Uzbek people cannot be imagined without traditional holidays and rituals, which are important stages of the life of Uzbeks. They contain deep emblems and images that reflect people's views on the world, their place in it. These are especially vividly represented by the ancient holiday of the spring equinox – Navruz. It is considered a time when the whole nature wakes up from hibernation, symbolizes renewal and rebirth. Ramadan, the month of fasting and spiritual purification, also occupies a great place in the life of the Uzbeks. This is a period of special piety and repentance, sincere prayer and family unity. Traditional weddings, New Years and funerals reflect the same deep connection between Uzbeks and their cultural roots, demonstrating the close connection of family values, religion and social customs.

The International Festival “Boysun spring”, which is considered a tourist season with a long-awaited and interesting vision of travelers from all over the world and lovers of Eastern ethnic culture, is held in the Boysun District of Surkhandarya region. A number of international media have already begun to show interest in this unique festival, among them the Sada al-Bilad (Egypt), the Organization for Economic Cooperation (IHT), the electronic portal of the Institute of Culture (headquartered in Tehran, Iran), the news agency “Fars News Agency” (Iran) and the China (PRC) information and analytical publications.

On April 5, 2022, the material published by the Egyptian publication “Sada al-Bilad” said that the traditional festival of folklore communities operating in Uzbekistan will be attended by more than 200 representatives, showcasing the traditions of costumes, songs and folklore unique to its region, and the province is seeing a heated presence at this festival. In an article published by the information portal of the Institute of culture of the organization of Economic Cooperation (eco) (Tehran, Republic of Iran) – during the meeting on April 6, 2022, this folklore holiday “Boysun-spring” will acquire international importance. “In 2001, the Boysun cultural space was included by UNESCO as” masterpieces of the oral and intangible heritage of humanity”, in may 2002, the first

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open Folklore Festival of people's performers of Uzbekistan, Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan was held in the Khushmanzor district, " the information portal said. Iran's largest news agency, the "Fars News Agency", also said in 2022

On may 7-8, The Folk Festival "Boysun spring" is held in Padang District of Boysun district, Surkhandarya region, in order to preserve centuries-old folk values and traditions. The beauty of Boysun, a popular territory of Uzbekistan, was listed by UNESCO as a masterpiece of "oral and intangible cultural heritage of humanity" and was included in the list of "intangible cultural heritage of humanity" in 2008-notes the Iranian news agency. The information and analytical publication" China "(PRC) also published an article about the upcoming Boysun Spring Festival, according to the world news agency. "National competitions in wrestling, ethnosport, velomarafon, Capricorn-multicar, varrak flying, chillac and other folk games occupy an important place in the festival, where our unique folk values and traditions are concentrated. At the end of the Festival, the winners of the best folklore-ethnographic teams, sports and folk games will be awarded with merit".

No culture can exist in a vacuum, Uzbek culture is no exception. Today, in the era of globalization and technology, Uzbekistan is trying to preserve its rich cultural heritage, and at the same time bring it into time. From museums and cultural centers that preserve and promote folk applied art, navqiran has been widely promoting educational programs and festivals in our country aimed at encouraging the generation to study and develop their cultural heritage. Uzbekistan actively participates in intercultural exchange, demonstrating its culture and traditions to the world and learning from others. Our national culture is inherited from generation to generation by our national values, customs, traditions and is widely promoted by the future generation all over the world.

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